

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A study of The professionalism of Administrative Personnel at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba, Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

Professionalism is a very important aspect of supporting the quality of school administration management. This research is a research that aims to determine the implementation of professionalism of the administrative workforce at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba. In this study using a qualitative descriptive study. The informants in this study were the principal, vice-principal, head of administrative staff, and administrative staff. The technique of collecting data through observation methods, interview methods, and documentation methods. The technique of data analysis in this study uses data collection techniques, data presentation, reduction, and conclusions. The results showed that the professionalism of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in their proficiency in using equipment and attitudes in school administrative services can be said to be good and quite satisfying. This is evident in the proficiency of administrative staff in operating all the equipment that supports their work and the friendly and polite attitude of administrative staff in providing services, especially in school administrative services. However, from the readiness, responsibility, and disciplinary attitude in implementing school administrative services, it is considered that they are still not good because there is still administrative staff who have not carried out their duties and responsibilities professionally. This will affect the quality and performance of the administrative staff on the professionalism of their work at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba.

Keywords: *Professionalism, administrative staff, school administration.*

INTRODUCTION

The administration is one element that has an important role in supporting the achievement of the goals of an organization (Akpınar & Kaptan, 2010; Niswaty, Juniati, Darwis, Salam, & Arhas, 2019; Witulski, 1993). Apart from administering human

resources, it is also the most important element in any organizational activity (Blaga & Jozsef, 2014; Čižiūnienė, Vaičiūtė, & Batarlienė, 2016; Wright, Dunford, & Snell, 2001). The success of an organization in achieving its goals and objectives as well as the ability to face various challenges is largely determined by the ability to manage human resources appropriately.

In school administration management, school administrative staff are professional education personnel (Sakuliampaiboon, Songkhla, & Sujiva, 2015; Shah, 2014; Sunar & Tabancali, 2012). Professional is a job that is directly related to the profession that is owned by someone so that they can apply it to the office administration that is in the school. Professionalism means the qualities that must be possessed by every professional in carrying out their work so that the work can be carried out and carried out as well as possible, full of responsibility with what they have done based on the education and skills they have. (Desselle, Raja, Andrews, & Lui, 2018; Hayward, 2006; Russell & Beaver, 2013).

Professionalism is a very important aspect in supporting the quality of school administration management because a professional administrative staff will be able to work properly by the demands of the job and prevailing norms (Amirullah & Darwis, 2015; Nasrullah, 2016; Niswaty & Saleh, 2015) needed in the world of education, to be able to provide effective and efficient administrative services so that the education process in the school will run by established procedures. (Alumuna et al 2017; Joo, 2020).

To produce professional administrative staff, various things need to be considered. Such as the management of human resources through education and training to produce professional personnel (Karatepe, 2013; Ozkeser, 2019; Semenova & Palin, 2015). Because the existence of professional human resources will have a big influence on the quality administrative service conditions. Administrative personnel occupies an important role as educational personnel whose duties are not only to assist schools in administrative matters but include several important activities in developing school quality such as management, development of supervision, and technical services.

The provisions or competency standards that a professional administrative staff must have are contained in the Regulation of the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 24 of 2008 concerning the standards for school/madrasah administrative staff, namely: (1) Personality Competencies These competencies include competence to have integrity and noble character, work ethic, self-control, self-confidence, flexibility, thoroughness, discipline, creative and innovative, responsibility. (2) Social Competence This competence includes competence to work in teams, excellent service, awareness in organization, effective communication, and building working relationships. (3) Technical Competence This competence includes competence to carry out personnel administration, finance, facilities and infrastructure, school relations with the community, correspondence and archiving, student administration, curriculum administration, special service administration, and application of communication and information technology (ICT). (4) Managerial Competence (especially for school/madrasah administrative heads) This competency includes competencies to support the management of national education standards, compile programs and work reports,

organize staff, develop staff, optimize resource utilization, foster staff, manage conflicts and compile the report.

The performance of school administrative personnel is one of the determining factors in achieving educational goals (Hadaway, 2005). The performance of administrative staff can be high if the competence of school administrative personnel is also adequate, resulting in the satisfaction of education services for service recipients (Esubalew & Raghurama, 2020; Göleç & Karadeniz, 2020; Yu & Ko, 2017). In achieving quality school administrative services, the professionalism of administrative personnel work is also the most urgent factor. Where professionalism is the embryo of achieving a quality school administrative service. Therefore, the professionalism of administrative personnel must be the focus of attention by related parties. Because, the higher the quality of existing administrative staff, the better the resulting performance, especially in terms of school administrative services.

Therefore, with this professional administrative staff, it is hoped that the administrative staff in each school will be able to create quality educational administrative services. As well as being an example and maintaining the good name of the institution by the trust that has been given to it. Considering that the professionalism of administrative personnel is very important to improve school administrative services, according to Martin Jr. (Nurbaiti, 2013) There are five characteristics of professionalism that are indicators of employee professionalism, namely proficiency in using equipment, readiness in service, responsibility for service, discipline, and attitude.

SMK Country 7 Bulukumba is an educational institution that seeks to create and implement the professionalism of its administrative staff to create a quality administrative service system. However, seeing the fact that the administration system implementation at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba still has weaknesses in the administrative system. This can be seen from the performance of the administrative staff that has not been maximal in implementing the school administrative service system, the number of administrative personnel is still lacking in achieving the maximum implementation of the administrative service system, and the administrative structuring system is not by what is expected.

METHOD

The variable studied in this study was a single variable, namely the Professionalism of Administrative Personnel at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba. This research is a qualitative descriptive study. (Sugiyono, 2017) Qualitative research is a research method based on the post-positivism philosophy, used to examine the condition of a natural object, (as opposed to an experiment) where the researcher is the key instrument, the sampling of data sources is done purposively and snowball, the collection technique is by triangulation (combined). , data analysis is inductive/qualitative, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization. The type of research used is descriptive research. Cooper (Sudaryono, 2018) explained that this type of descriptive research is "research conducted to determine the value of the independent variable, either one or more (independent) variables without making comparisons, or connecting with other variables".

This research is focused on the professionalism of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba to improve the quality school administrative service system. The

data sources in this study were the principal, vice-principal, head of administrative staff, and administrative staff. This study also used data validity techniques. The validity of the data is intended to obtain a level of trustworthiness related to how far the research results are correct. The data validity technique used in this study is the extension of the observation where the technique of extending the observation is carried out to increase the credibility/trust of the data. With the extension of the observation, it means that the researcher returns to the field, makes observations, and interviews again with the data sources that are found or with newer data sources. Data collection techniques used are interview techniques, observation, and documentation, and data analysis techniques used in this research are using data collection techniques, data presentation, reduction, and the conclusion.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Administrative work professionalism is a form of the ability of administrative staff to carry out their duties and responsibilities in providing administrative services effectively and efficiently. Professional administrative staff will be able to work optimally so that they will be able to create innovations to achieve a professional administrative service system but still make the goals of the institution as a reference in completing their duties and responsibilities as school administrative service providers.

The professionalism of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba must work based on the principles of service delivery, namely, the principles of administrative skills in using equipment, the readiness of administrative personnel in providing services, responsibility for service, discipline, and attitude of administrative staff in providing services, especially administrative services. school.

Administrative Personnel Skills in Using Equipment

Proficiency is an element related to knowledge and skills acquired from education and training and experience. The professionalism of administrative personnel is very much determined by the level of ability or expertise they have which is reflected in their daily behavior. The term refers to the potential that administrative personnel has in carrying out their duties and parts.

Based on the results of interviews conducted with several informants regarding the indicators of proficiency of administrative personnel in using equipment, it can be concluded that the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba are good at operating all the tools that support their work. Administrative personnel is also proficient and competent in their duties and functions in terms of school administration services.

The foregoing is also confirmed by the extension of the observations described in the table below:

Table 1.
Administrative Personnel Skills in Using Equipment

No	Descriptor	Assessment	
		Good	Not good
1.	Utilizing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for smooth implementation of school administration	√	-
2.	Using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to document school administration	√	-

Based on table 1, it can be illustrated that the proficiency of administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in operating equipment that supports their work, in this case, can be seen from the use and use of information and communication technology in the implementation of school administration.

The readiness of administrative personnel in providing services

The readiness of administrative personnel in providing services is needed. The ability to help and provide fast (responsive) and precise service to someone, with clear information delivery. Based on the results of interviews with several informants related to the readiness indicators of administrative personnel in providing services, it was concluded that the readiness of administrative personnel at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in school administrative services was still considered to be less than optimal, administrative personnel was still very overwhelmed in completing work this was due to the lack of administrative personnel. at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in supporting the success of school administrative services. However, in terms of the delivery of information concerning administrative completeness is quite good, the information conveyed is explained in detail so that teachers and students as service recipients can understand well. The results of the interviews were also strengthened through the extension of the observations made:

Table 2.
The readiness of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

No	Descriptor	Assessment	
		Good	Not good
1.	Strive for quality work	√	-
2.	Acting quickly and precisely	-	√
3.	Get work done on time	-	√
4.	Delivery of Information	√	-

Based on table 2, it is illustrated that the readiness of administrative personnel to act quickly and appropriately is still considered not good enough so that they cannot complete the work on time. However, efforts to provide quality work are also very concerned, such as in the delivery of information, always providing accurate information by first seeing and learning about the importance of information to be conveyed to school principals, teachers, and students. So that the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in terms of providing information can already be considered good.

Responsibilities of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

The demand for accountability for every activity carried out for the benefit of many people is important for the operation of a good service system based on trust. Based on the results of interviews conducted by several that the responsibilities of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in terms of seriousness and work initiative are still not optimal, this can be seen from the lack of attention to the arrangement of documents in the filing cabinets, there is still work pending as well as in storing documents or archives, some are missing or scattered. The results of the interviews were also corroborated through the extension of the observations described in Table 3:

Table 3.
Responsibilities of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

No	Descriptor	Assessment	
		Good	Not good
1.	Coordinating and carrying out correspondence administration activities	-	√
2.	Coordinating and carrying out archiving administrative activities	-	√
3.	Fill in a diary planner	√	-
4.	Put together a program	-	√
5.	Coordinating the implementation of school activities	√	-
6.	Load monthly reports	√	-

Based on table 3, it can be illustrated that the duties and responsibilities of administrative personnel in terms of filling in the daily agenda book, coordinating the implementation of school activities, and preparing monthly reports have been considered good. However, there are still several duties and responsibilities of administrative personnel which is considered to be inadequate in their implementation, such as the implementation of correspondence and filing administration and the preparation of work programs. The administrative staff here are considered to be able to carry out all their duties, but not all administrative staff duties can be completed properly because there are still several factors that become observers in their implementation, both writing instruments, as well as computers that sometimes cannot be used, or even awareness and awareness. care for the

administrative staff itself. Therefore, the implementation of the duties and responsibilities of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba is still considered ineffective and inefficient.

Discipline

Discipline is a mental attitude and self-control possessed by a person or group which can be seen from their actions and behavior towards obedience to regulations or policies established by an agency. Discipline is also one of the factors that measure the good or bad performance of an institution, be it government agencies or private institutions (Ncha 2011; Bubu & Offiong 2014).

Theoretically, loyalty relates to the level of discipline, especially in terms of obedience to applicable regulations. Discipline will be well manifested if employees can comply with existing regulations. Loyalty is also closely related to the ability to be responsible for job duties and responsiveness. Also, loyalty does not discriminate in service delivery based on certain groups.

From the results of interviews conducted with several informants, it was found that the administrative staff's discipline was still considered poor. This can be seen from the lack of awareness of administrative staff in complying with regulations, such as office dating and returning hours. Therefore the discipline of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba needs to be improved so that the quality of the administrative system services at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba is even better.

The foregoing is also confirmed by the extension of the observations described in the table below:

Table 4.

Discipline

No	Descriptor	Assessment	
		Good	Not Good
1.	Managing time	-	√
2.	Comply with applicable regulations	-	√
3.	Attendance	-	√

Based on table 4, it can be seen that the discipline of administrative personnel is still not maximal. Administrative staff in managing time and obeying applicable regulations are still deemed not good, they have not been able to regulate office hours so that administrative staff still arrive late, as well as office hours there is still administrative personnel who leave earlier than office hours. This can be seen from the attendance of administrative staff. With this attendance, we can measure the level of discipline that administrative personnel has. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of discipline of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba is still considered very low.

The attitude of Administrative Staff in Providing Services

Everyone in an organization has the skills, attitudes, and knowledge needed to provide a particular service. Polite attitude, respect, attention, friendliness, and good communication in the sense of providing information to the public in a language they understand, and always listening to public suggestions and complaints. The professionalism of administrative personnel in the administrative service system at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba must meet the principles of politeness and hospitality. An administrative staff ready to provide services must be polite, friendly, neat, and clean. Based on the results of interviews with several informants related to indicators of the attitude of administrative staff in providing services, it can be concluded that the attitude of administrative staff in providing services, especially in the school administrative service system, has been implemented very well. This is also reinforced by the extension of the observations described in table 5:

Table 5.
The Attitude of Administrative Staff in Providing Services

No	Descriptor	Assessment	
		Good	Not Good
1.	Be friendly and polite	√	-
2.	Easy to contact	√	-
3.	Communicative	√	-

Based on table 5, it can be illustrated that the attitude of administrative personnel in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as providers of school administration services has been considered good. Administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukuma have described excellent service where this can be seen from the friendly and polite attitude that administrative staff has and the ease when communicating has been implemented very well.

DISCUSSION

The proficiency of Administrative Personnel in Using Equipment

Based on the findings in the field, it shows that the administrative staff in general has mastered all the work which is their main task and function. It can be seen that personally, the administrative staff have carried out their duties and functions properly. The skill of the administrative staff in operating all the equipment makes all the work that is done can be done easily. Proficiency here can be seen from the extent to which administrative staff can operate all equipment properly, correctly, and easily provide services, especially in school administrative services, because the more proficient the results are shown by the administrative staff, all the work given will also be quickly resolved. Based on research results (setiyowatidessysiti, 2010) found that one of the efforts

to control risks to the workforce is the application of correct use of equipment After administrative control, to create a safe work environment and increase occupational safety and health.

The Readiness of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

Based on the results of records in the field that the readiness of administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in providing administrative services is not optimal because the administrative staff is often reminded repeatedly about the work given this is because the number of administrative personnel is still very minimal so that it makes administrative personnel overwhelmed in completing it. work. The readiness of administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in providing administrative services in terms of delivering information related to administrative completeness gets a positive impression. In submitting information, administrative personnel explains in detail so that teachers and students as recipients of the information are facilitated and are not overwhelmed in understanding the information presented. Research result (Wanri, Rahayu, & Trigono, 2018) that to maximize the quality of service, the best way to do this is to select administrative personnel who are competent in the field of administration and conduct regular training.

Responsibilities of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

The findings in the field illustrate that the sense of responsibility that administrative personnel has for the work program at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba is also reflected in the seriousness they have in carrying out their duties. The ability of administrative staff to complete all work in an initiative and responsibly is still considered less effective and efficient. There is still some work that cannot be completed on time, and there is very little concern for the arrangement of archival documents. The characteristics of being responsible for the job are still not able to provide a good contribution to the professionalism of administrative personnel because this is considered to be less than optimal so that it affects the performance of administrative personnel in completing their work.

Administrative Staff Discipline

The findings in the field illustrate that there is still a lack of professionalism in the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba which can be seen from the lack of discipline in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Based on the findings in the field, it shows that some of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba still show a lack of discipline in carrying out the work program which is their responsibility. If the administrative staff is not disciplined, in the sense that there are still administrative staff who often arrive late past office hours, or go home earlier than office hours, how can the administrative staff work well, this will only make the performance of the administrative staff worse. Research result (Saleh, 2014) found that discipline is an effort to improve the quality of employees.

The attitude of Administrative Personnel in Providing Services

The friendliness of administrative staff in providing administrative services has been implemented well, they can inspire confidence and comfort to those who need services. The friendly attitude possessed by administrative staff will be a determining factor for service recipients in providing a good assessment of the services provided. The courtesy of the administrative staff in providing administrative services will determine the comfort for the service recipients themselves. Because by having a polite attitude, the service recipients will not feel awkward and feel not burdened or afraid to disturb and so on. This has become an obligation for service providers in serving anyone who needs service and everyone's right is to get good service. Therefore, to realize a quality service system, it is expected that polite and friendly attitudes need to be improved because this involves the public interest and this attitude must of course be based on the genuineness of the heart of each service provider so that it is not comfortable in providing services sincerely.

CONCLUSION

Administrative work professionalism is the level of ability and expertise possessed in carrying out tasks and responsibilities so that it can be carried out with high quality, on time, and always based on procedures that are easy to understand and understand. The professionalism of the administrative staff at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba in their proficiency in using equipment and attitudes in school administrative services can be said to be good and quite satisfying. This is evident in the proficiency of administrative staff in operating all the equipment that supports their work and the friendly and polite attitude of administrative staff in providing services, especially in school administrative services. there is still administrative personnel who have not carried out their duties and responsibilities professionally. This will affect the quality and performance of the administrative staff on the professionalism of their work at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba.

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